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Is Q for DQ? Applying Q-methodology for Researching Digital Intelligence

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Abstract: *Most approaches to investigating research topics in the field of education and educational psychology are based on objectivity criteria. In some cases, subjective perceptions are considered to be biased and unreliable. The present paper draws upon a growing interest in emphasizing the use of Q-methodology in the field of education research. The article suggests that Q-methodology could be appealing for the research of digital intelligence as well as for other topics related to the area of education research. This positional paper aims to expand knowledge about the use of subjective methodologies and to set theoretical and methodological grounds to apply this specific methodology in the process of data collection and analysis. Therefore, the article depicts a corpus of scholar opinions to analyzing the concept of digital intelligence. Given that the concept of digital intelligence has a strong self-explanatory note, most of the authors preferred omnibus definitions for its enlightenment. The authors assert the need to formulate a definition of the construct rather than focusing on its dimensions. Thus, they use the Cattell–Horn–Carroll theory (CHC model) of intelligence to create the definition of digital intelligence. Based on this theoretical ground, methodological considerations and case studies are discussed in relation to applying Q-methodology to researching subjective views of students. The Q-methodology is described as an approach to providing a systematic study of the human subjectivity. Drawing on a study on digital intelligence, the utility of the method is illustrated. To expand the use of the Q-methodology, relevant examples of studies conducted by other authors are discussed.*

Keywords: *Q-methodology; Digital Intelligence; Subjectivity; Factor Analysis.*

I. INTRODUCTION

People in everyday life make many appreciations and evaluations of persons, things, and situations. Many of these evaluations are done quickly, casually, and intuitively. These impressions may be extremely relevant in understanding an individual or social perspective on a specific subject. In order to convert these subjective impressions into valuable insights in the process of researching a social phenomenon, the researchers need to ensure that they are *commensurable*. In pursuit of this desideratum, Q Methodology (QM) has been proven empirically reliable.

Sometimes known as ‘Q sorting’, QM encompasses a distinctive set of psychometric and operational principles and provides the researcher with a solid study of human subjectivity [12].

Most approaches to investigating research topics in the field of education and educational psychology are based on objectivity criteria. In some cases, subjective perceptions are considered to be biased and unreliable. Subjectivity, understood as a personal point of view, is thought not to be easy to approach. As other scholars do, we believe there is an answer to the question ‘How to research subjectivity?’ Correspondingly, the paper focuses on the QM as an appropriate answer. Our primary goal is to set the stage for applying QM in the process of researching the digital intelligence (DQ).

Thus, in the first section of the paper, we focus on defining the concept of DQ. As a newborn concept, DQ lacks a solid theoretical basis. Thus, we draw upon on a new emerging theoretical model. The second section has a more practical mark since we intend to describe the steps for applying Q methodology. Various studies are analyzed in the subsections called ‘Theoretical foundations’. The case of DQ is discussed in the subsections called ‘Case in point’.

II. DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE: BABY STEPS AND NEAR FUTURE

There is no doubt that the intelligence has been defined in so many different ways. The intelligence is a multi-faceted construct, referring to both a process and an aptitude, to a shape or an attribute of the human mind and behavior [15]. Two decades ago, the American Psychological Association (APA) established a task force to work on clarifying what is known and unknown in relation to intelligence [13]. In the report published in 1996, APA states that the concept of intelligence is expected to clarify differences among individuals in terms of their capabilities to understand complex ideas, to solve problems, to react to life situations [13]. It is important to underline that the report’s authors use the term ‘concepts of intelligence’, suggesting the variety of understandings of this construct. As Adams put it into his article [2], the concept of intelligence may refer to a subjective and personal way of using knowledge to interact with the environment. The human-computer interaction resulted in a new way of intelligence that merely can be observed: DQ. Most of the definitions focus on structural elements of DQ. DQ Institute (which coined the acronym in 2016) defines the concept as the sum of technical, mental and social competencies essential to digital life [6]. Following the Cattell–Horn–Carroll theory of cognitive abilities (CHC theory) [9], we consider a three-stratum model where DQ is understood as a *general ability*. According to DQ Institute, eight *broad abilities* can be identified: (1) *Digital identity*; (2) *Digital use*; (3) *Digital safety*; (4) *Digital security*; (5) *Digital emotional intelligence*; (6) *Digital communication*; (7) *Digital literacy*; (8) *Digital rights*. Each dimension encompasses three narrow abilities [14] - see Figure 1. For example, digital emotional intelligence (as a broad ability) encompasses *empathy*, *social* and *emotional awareness*, and *emotional regulation* (as narrow abilities).

Figure 1. The three-stratum model of DQ

III. Q METHODOLOGY

As stated in *Introduction*, this section is intended to provide a comprehensive approach for applying Q methodology in the study of DQ. In this light, we discuss methodological principles and aspects to be taken into account in the process of researching the human subjectivity in relation with the mentioned topic.

3.1. Theoretical grounds: history and methodological principles

The roots of QM are in the work of Stephenson, published in 1935. The author suggested that the conventional factor analysis could be inverted [21]. This outstanding methodological innovation has shifted focus from subjects to opinions and subjectivity. Consequently, a core principle of the

methodology is the *subjective communicability* [12]. McKeown and Thomas agree that this principle runs counter to information theory. In doing so, QM achieves to measure the responses and their meanings associated to a specific information.

The subjective reactions and the way in which they are communicated conduct to revealing another pillar of QM, namely *the concourse of communication* [12]. As Stephenson states, the concept of concourse stands parallel to target population in traditional sampling. It refers to the volume of discussions regarding a subject. Thus, it encompasses a variety of means of expressions: perceptions, representations, opinions, beliefs, thoughts or emotions that have already been expressed. In other terms, the concourses encompass a pool of raw meanings. They represent the first scaffold in discovering the perspective on the analyzed topic.

Starting from the concourse, a number of representative allegations (attributes and attributions, as Block suggests [4]) are selected. These result in a *Q sample*. Having in mind a sampling procedure, the researcher will need to assure representativeness of these allegations [12]. Once the Q sample has been selected, the next step will be to be presented it to subjects participating in a Q methodological project. The participants form the P-set which will perform a Q sorting operation. Namely, they will sort the items according to the measure in which they agree or disagree with the respective allegation. As Brown [5] concludes, the Q sorting is a model of communication through which the researcher gains access to the subjective meaning associated to an item in a given context.

In summary, a number of sequences can be identified when conducting a Q methodological study:

- (1) The concourse of communication is sampled, resulting in the Q sample.
- (2) A sample of subjects, the P-set, is selected.
- (3) The participants sort the items in the Q sample according to their subjective interpretation and following a condition of instruction.
- (4) The Q sort data is analyzed.
- (5) Conclusively, factor interpretation is achieved.

In the subsequent sections, the aforementioned steps are discussed and illustrated.

3.2. The concourses of communication

3.2.1. Theoretical foundations

As coined by Stephenson in 1986, the concourse of communication defines the sum on any communication on a topic of interest. Klaus, Wingreen, and Blanton [10] define the concourse of communication as an existing ‘states’ of communicability in relation to a specific domain or subject. It is suggested that the subject is interpreted in multiple subjective manners. Thus, one of the main characteristics of a concourse of communication is being multi-layered **Error! Reference source not found.** The subjective impressions could be identified in venues ranging from internet sources (such as forums, social media pages, blogs) to scientific research databases. Prey [16] focused on the ‘circulation, popularization and utilization of revolutionary ideologies within the ‘concourse of communication’ in the South Korean student movement since 1980. In the view of the cited author, the concourse of communication is a ‘space’ of framed and re-framed lived experience of conscious human beings. In a more recent study, Klaus, Wingreen, and Blanton [10] applied the Concourse Theory and QM to research the types of Enterprise System users and their preferred management strategies. In the case of this research, the concourse was defined using transcripts of focus groups.

3.2.2. Case in point: researching DQ

As mentioned in the section dedicated to the conceptualization of DQ, there is no previous research largely focusing on this concept. Many of the internet available resources discuss DQ in relation with organizations not with individuals. Thus, research in the field is meant to develop technologies, capabilities, and practices that organizations can use in their specific field of activity.

An illustration of the discourse of communication regarding DQ may include the following examples:

- ‘Digital intelligence involves understanding your customers and how they’re using your website, mobile site or mobile app, then using this data to optimize their experience no matter when, where or how they interact with you’, is mentioned on AT internet website [1].
- ‘A simple definition of Digital intelligence is “the ability to acquire and apply new knowledge and skills related to digital technologies”. It is more than the ability to use digital tools, but rather than know why, know what, know how and know when of digital technology to improve effectiveness and outcomes. Digital Intelligence is fundamentally about our relationship with technology’, says Simon Waller, the author of *The Digital Champion: Connecting the Dots between People, Work and Technology* [20].
- ‘The antidote is digital intelligence which represents a strategic shift in approach to marketing analysis that uses insights from traditional and modern channels (we’re talking online AND offline) to enable actionable, customer-obsessed analytical brilliance’ [8].
- And finally, DQ Institute defines DQ as the sum of technical, mental and social competencies essential to digital life [6].

As stated above, we have engaged in a process of setting the ground for the use of the DQ concept within the field of education. In our research, the discourse of communication was defined starting from the verbatim transcripts of four focus groups conducted with undergraduate students. The focus groups revolved around the main factors of DQ explained in the above section. We were interested in finding experiences, feelings, emotions, thoughts, and beliefs associated with subjects’ digital life. The focus groups recordings were transcribed, read and re-read several times. The theoretical framework of DQ assured that selected affirmations covered all relevant aspects of DQ.

3.3. Sampling the Q set

3.3.1. Theoretical foundations

QM relies on two types of sampling: (1) *the sample of allegations to be sorted* - the Q sample (N) and (2) *the sample of subjects - P-set* (n). The Q sample is of primary importance. The selection of allegations from the discourses follows the principle of *representative design* advanced by Brunswick and theoretically grounded by Stephenson [17]. As in conventional sampling, Q samples do not include all the discourses but a selection of affirmations to offer a comprehensive representation of the topic. As Watts and Stenner suggest, the Q sample is a ‘collection of heterogeneous items’ [21]. Two approaches could be used to sample the statements namely an *unstructured procedure* and a *structured one*. The first type of sampling refers to a corpus of means of selection intended to assure a comprehensive coverage without applying experimental design principles [12]. In the case of structured samples, experimental design principles are applied. Each item is assigned to an experimental condition according to Fisher [7]. Watts and Stenner recommend to previously set a well-defined research question which will act as a ‘condition of instruction’ for the subjects [21]. In the authors’ view, the Q sample would represent possible answers to this research question.

3.3.2. Case in point

To research the discourses of DQ, we have put in place a similar approach to that applied by Berkhout et al. [3]. All the transcripts have been read and re-read. A number of 182 statements have been selected in the first phase. To assure that the statements cover the complex structure of DQ, the conceptual framework designed in the second section of the paper has been used. Not all the dimensions had an equal number of corresponding statements. The set of statements has been discussed by the research team during two meetings. The statements have been analyzed for semantic redundancy, clarity or ambiguity. An unstructured sampling procedure has been applied. Some of the statements were eliminated. Others were rephrased. Since the eight dimensions of DQ encompass various specific abilities, we considered that each dimension needs to be covered by at least 6 statements. This resulted in a Q sample of 78 statements. Closed group card sort question type (Survey Gizmo®; Boulder, CO) was preferred to sort the statements. The subjects were invited to sort the statements on a continuum from ‘agree - disagree’ (-5 to +5 grid).

3.4. Sampling the P-set

3.4.1. Theoretical foundations

As argued before, when conducting a Q methodological project, the focus is on the Q sample rather than on the P-set. Nevertheless, the P-set or P sample is still important [12]. Comparing to surveys or other methodologies, QM is an intensive mode of analysis. Hence, the number of persons participating in the research is not of primary importance. As Berkhout et al. [3] state, there is no definite number of subjects in Q projects. In a study investigating patterns in self-regulated learning, the authors [3] sampled 75 students. The researchers set no specific criteria to recruit the participants. In another study conducted by Young and Shepardson [19], 15 undergraduate students were sampled to participate in. Yildirim [18] conducted a Q study to identify the students' perceptions on the gamification of learning in an academic course. The P-set included 34 subjects. Another illustration of the number of subjects in a Q study focuses on the research conducted by Koutsoftas, Dubasik, and Moss DiDonato [11]. The researched aimed to expand knowledge on the instructional practices in preschool education. The P-set included 150 teachers who sorted 80 affirmations referring to common instructional practices. In all the cited studies, the criterion of selection had a nonrandom nature, being based on subjects' availability. McKeown and Thomas [12] suggest that, in addition to convenience and availability criteria, *factorial designs* could be employed to sample persons in a P-set. In Q methodology, a 3:1 ratio of statements to number of participants is best, but a 2:1 ratio is also acceptable, argue Webler et al., 2009 as cited by Young and Shepardson [19].

3.4.2. Case in point: DQ

In the study we have conducted, no eligibility criteria were set, excepting being an undergraduate student. Since the allegations in the Q sample were sorted via Survey Gizmo platform® (Boulder, CO), the researchers were responsible for the dissemination of the link through which the subjects had access to the Q sample. In sampling the P-set, we focused on achieving a diverse sample of undergraduates. The diversity was defined in terms of the fields and programs of study the students were enrolled in. Thus, the snowball sampling procedure was preferred. A total number of 172 subjects have sorted the Q sample.

3.5. Analysis of the Q sorted data

3.5.1. Theoretical foundations

By person factor analysis is required to analyze the Q sorted data [12]. Specific software is available to support data analysis (e.g. Q Assessor, PQMethod Software, KenQ Analysis, PCQ). The technique creates clusters of persons who share the same viewpoints, by focusing on similarities among individuals. The main distinction between Q and R methodologies consists in correlating and factoring persons instead of items in QM studies [12]. McKeown and Thomas apprise for reluctance when interpreting QM as an inverted factor analysis [12].

3.5.2. Case in point: DQ

Based on Thurston's centroid analysis, we identified three main segments or clusters within the P-set. These clusters describe segments of persons who are or not equipped with digital skills to maximize their digital experience and to minimize the threats. Since our intention was to focus more on practical and methodological aspects, we decided to not describe the characteristics of clusters in this paper.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The paper aimed to explore to what extent QM is an appropriate approach to investigating DQ. As stated in *Introduction*, there is no extensive research addressing this relatively new concept. Thus, the paper has been built on the theoretical model proposed by DQ Institute. We believe a hierarchical model with three strata could explain better the concept of DQ. Within the model, DQ is understood as a general ability, encompassing eight broad abilities and twenty four narrow abilities. Given the lack of theoretical foundation, we considered that DQ could benefit from subjective viewpoints of the undergraduates rather than a confirmatory factor analysis. Hence, the model has

been used to develop a Q methodological study. Drawing upon the eight dimensions of the DQ, we have identified the discourse of communication on this topic. In the next step, the researchers discussed and refined the statements in order to reduce them to a more manageable Q sample. The 78 statements have been sorted according to the extent to which the P-set agree or not with them. The collected data have been analyzed and resulted in a very insightful psychographic segmentation of the P-set.

Following these steps, the paper presented the theoretical rationale and explained the particularities of QM in researching DQ. In summary, QM offers a valuable and systematic means to research subjective viewpoints. In the case of DQ, QM, as an exploratory approach, offered two future actionable research directions. One of them is related to the segments identified within the P-set. For educational purposes, it is extremely important to raise awareness about the strengths and vulnerabilities of the undergraduate students in relation to their digital life. The second direction supports the empirical validation of the three-stratum model of DQ using R approaches.

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